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OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Abdullayev Salmonbek Murodali o`g`li

**BIOLOGIYA DARSLARIDA ELEKTRON DARSLIKLARDAN
FOYDALANISH**

DRJI

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WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

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EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

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